

Equity, Access and Inclusion in Higher Education in India

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India has a unique culture and is one of the oldest and greatest civilizations of the world. She has a variegated society comprising individuals of many religions, languages, ethnicity and culture. India has attracted peoples from various parts of the world throughout the history. The foreigners came as invaders but later settled in India and they became a part and parcel of her rich composite culture. The tolerance and assimilation have been the chief characteristics of Indian culture. This is why; to a foreigner Indian society appears as mosaic of cultures. Despite of this all pervasive diversity, a current of unity has always been there underneath.

All are borne almost equal; variations are only of biological and psychological nature. But our society ascribes different status to individual based on various ascriptive considerations such as gender, ethnicity, caste, religion etc. Education should work for removing inequalities in the society and building an egalitarian social order. The provision for educational facilities is not evenly available to all sections in every geographical area. The education in general and higher education in particular is creating and widening inequalities instead of reducing them. The unequal access to higher education coupled with other factors perpetuates a cycle of poverty. In our country, not only the poor are at receiving ends but some other ascriptive considerations too play a decisive role in access to higher education. These ascriptive considerations are- gender, caste and religion. The feudal elements still have an upper hand in governments, policy formulation and their implementation. There is an awakening in hitherto disadvantaged sections of society and they have started asserting their rights.

Provision of facilities for higher education needs to be expanded. The Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) at higher education is 12.4 in India, whereas the Global average is at 23. The GER for some of advanced nations is still higher e.g. it is about 60 in U.S.A. & Canada and over 40 in several European countries. An overview of GER of various nations across the world makes it evident that developed nations have higher GER than that in developing and underdeveloped nations. The 21st century characterized by knowledge economy, makes it imperative for all nations to develop their education system in general and higher education in particular to achieve a developed economy. India, the second most populous country on the globe has more than half of its population below age of 25 years. India can reap the benefits of its young population in the form of demographic only if it develops a sound system of higher education.

There is an urgent need not only to increase GER at the level of higher education but also to provide equal opportunity to all sections of society in admission in higher educational institutions. In India higher education is not inclusive, some

sections of the society are over represented and others are conspicuous by their meager presence. The Scheduled Castes (SCs), Scheduled Tribes (STs), Other Backward Classes (OBCs), Minorities, Women and the

Poor- a group cutting across all other social groups, constitute the disadvantaged sections - in Indian society. These groups due to one or another reason are Underrepresented in higher education. The socially higher sections and upper class & upper middle class are the major beneficiaries of subsidized higher education. The revenues needed for maintenance of government and aided institutions of higher learning come from the taxes, mainly from indirect ones. So the poor are at receiving- end and the rich are reaping the benefits of subsidized higher education. With better prospects of employment after higher education, the sons and daughters of the rich get better employment and add to the wealth of already affluent sections of the society. The education system in India is perpetuating and nurturing inequality in the society.

This paper deals with having a stock of unequal representation of various disadvantaged sections, interventions for their inclusion and suggestion for making these interventions really meaningful and effect. Let's first discuss about the disadvantaged groups of Indian society and the causes for their poor representation in education, particularly in higher education.

The Scheduled Castes

Scheduled castes constitute about 15% of Indian population. Their economic and social condition is very deplorable. The cause of their utter backwardness is rooted in history and religion. A dominant section of Indian society propagated a false notion of origin of these so called scheduled castes from the feet's of Lord Brahma and gave them a very low status in the society, while claiming themselves as the highest among Hindus. This purity-pollution theory is basis of social stratification among the caste Hindu. These self-styled social contractors even today try to keep scheduled castes and other disadvantaged sections of society out of mainstream of the nation, culture and society. The utter poverty coupled with social backwardness of SCs is the root cause of their backwardness in education in general and higher education in particular.

The socio-religious reforms, beginning in 14th century A.D., tried to ameliorate the poor condition of this section and condemned the practice of untouchability. The advent of Europeans in the country with the modern thoughts of rationality, equality, liberty and individualism led to social reform movements in 19th century, which had made their social status somewhat better. The anti-untouchability movement under the leadership of Mahatma Gandhi and Dr. B.R Ambedkar aroused an awakening among these and they started themselves urging for their rights and more participation in society and governance.

The Scheduled Tribes

The Scheduled Tribes (STs) constitute about 7.5% of Indian population. They inhabit hilly and forest areas with very adverse conditions. According to Article 342 of the Constitution, the Scheduled Tribes are the tribes or tribal communities or part of or groups within these tribes and tribal communities which have been declared as such by the President through a public notification. STs constitute a very heterogeneous group but they all are socially, economically and educationally disadvantaged. Some STs have their own language and scripts quite different from that of the mainstream groups. The poverty, language difference, shyness and over attachment to their culture and nature had resulted in their educational backwardness.

Other Backward Classes

Our Constitution speaks of socially and educationally backward classes, whose social and educational status is not at par with the higher sections of the society. The Other Backward Classes are other than SCs and STs. Unlike SCs they are not considered as untouchables. OBCs constitute a major chunk, approximately 54% of Indian population (Mandal Commission). So this large group of citizens can't be ignored because their education will, beyond doubt, add to the prosperity of nation. Though this group has access to land resources and they have conspicuous presence in politics of the day but they are not adequately represented in education and government services.

Women

Women also more or less disadvantaged in every society across the world. The patriarchal society like ours wants to keep them within four walls of the home. The girls are considered to be a liability on the family and it is a general tendency among masses that they are not assets of the family. It may be, because the educated girl with the prospect of higher earnings does not serve the home of his parents but the benefits of her higher education are reaped by her in-laws and spouse. So parents do not consider it a wise investment and they try to give only a minimum or average level of education to their girls, suffice to help in arranging a spouse for her. The poverty also hinders the education of children more particularly girls. The son preference ideology of classical Hinduism has also deteriorated the general position of girls and so their education also. The lack of facilities for higher education in rural, hilly, tribal and remote areas is a big obstacle in the way of guardians who are even willing to send their daughters to schools. The age, at which girls enter the arena of higher education, the parents start too much bothering about their marriage. So girls have to break their studies at the cost of marriage and eventually they get involved in petty household works. These all factors make girls disadvantaged vis-a-vis boys in the field of higher education.

Minorities

Besides SCs, STs, OBCs and women, minorities also constitute the educationally backward class in Indian society. The constitution of India mentions two types of minorities-linguistic and religious; but does not provide definition of any of these. The National Commission for Minorities Act 1993 empowers the president and governors to declare the name of minority groups. In the pursuance of the act, Muslim, Sikh, Christian, Buddhist and Parsis have been declared as minority groups in India. These constitute 18.6% of the Indian population with Muslims 13.4%, Christians Sikhs 2.3%, Sikhs 1.9% and Buddhist 0.8% (Census 2001).

The Poor

Apart from aforesaid all conventionally recognized disadvantaged sections of society, there is a group cutting across all other social and religious groups, the poor. Poverty is the characteristic and sole identity of this group. Though the higher education in government institutions particularly liberal education is highly subsidized, but the poor is not able to pay even that meager fee. The poor fail to compete with others coming from affluent sections of the society in admission tests. Even many fail to get the minimum qualification (12th standard) with the requisite marks to have access to institutions of higher learning. The other related expenditures like maintenance charges, travel expenses, “accommodation expenses, books and stationery are too much and are beyond the economic capacity of the poor. Even in government and aided institutions the fee charges of professional and technical education is very high. The new culture of self -finance courses in government institutions add to the miseries of the poor. The higher education imparted in the private institutions is even. beyond the imagination of talented but the poor. The winds of liberalization, privatization and globalization have too added to the woes of the poor. The market do not care for the poor, it cares for only those who can participate in it.

The following section deals with Constitutional provisions and various schemes and programmes run by the government to cater the need of education in general and higher education in particular of disadvantaged sections.

Interventions

The interventions can be discussed as the provisions made in the Constitution and schemes of government favouring inclusion of hitherto educationally disadvantaged sections of society.

Constitutional Provisions

The founding fathers of independent India were well versed with the need of expansion of avenues for higher education for masses with special provisions for disadvantaged and weaker sections of society. They believed in socialistic pattern of society and their nation building efforts were based on egalitarian philosophy, for this very reason they incorporated some special provisions in the constitution

regarding positive discrimination in the favor of women, SCs, STs & other socially and educationally backward sections of the society.

The Constitutional provisions proclaims equality before the law and equal protection of laws each and every individual of the society (Art. 14) and prohibits discrimination on grounds of religion, race, caste, sex or place of birth only (Art 15). Constitution also provides right to minorities to establish and administer educational institutions of their choice (Art. 29). The State shall not, in granting aid to educational institutions, discriminate against any educational institution on the ground that it is under the management of a minority, whether based on religion or language (Art 30).

Policy, Schemes and Programmes The central as well as state governments have taken various steps for promotion of education among weaker sections of the society for building a classless and casteless society. The very first National policy on Education of Independent India (NPE, 1968) had mentioned that strenuous efforts should be made to equalize educational opportunities.

The policy urged for reducing regional imbalances in the provision of educational facilities. It also recommended for adoption of common school system on the lines of Education Commission (1964-66). It opined for more intensive efforts to develop education among the backward classes, especially among the tribal people. Regarding minorities education, the NPE 1968 had provisions for promotion of educational interests of minorities. National Policy on Education, 1986 emphasized on the removal of disparities and to equalize educational opportunities by attending to specific needs of those who have been denied equality so far.

In the following paragraphs a bird-eye view has been made of ongoing government programs, projects and schemes for expansion, access, equity and inclusion of disadvantaged sections in higher education.

Expansion- The central government is giving special emphasis on expansion of higher education. The 11th five year plan is regarded as a plan of higher education. There are 504 Universities and university level institutions-243 state universities, 53 state private universities, 40 central universities, 130 institutions deemed to be universities, 33 institutes of national importance and 5 institutes established by the states. Government is vet) keen to establish new institutions of higher learning and is also encouraging the private efforts for establishing new institutions. The Table 1 gives a summary of expansion of higher education during XI Plan.

Table 1: Establishment of New Central Higher Education Institutions

SN	Type of Institution	Number	
		At the end of X plan	To be estsd in XI Plan
1	Central Universities	19	16+14*

2	IITs	7	8
3	NITs	20	10
4	IIITs	4	20
5	IISERs	2	3
6	IIMs	6	1
7	SPAs	1	2

*14 Innovation Universities aiming at World Class standards are proposed across XI and XII Plan period.

New Degree Colleges

The Government of India proposes to establish one Model Degree College in each of Educationally Backward Districts where Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) is lower than national average. An amount of 782 crore has been earmarked for establishing 200 such colleges during XI Plan.

These schemes are for expansion of educational opportunities for all sections of society, These efforts will definitely benefit the weaker and disadvantaged sections of the society as there is reservation for them in admission to educational institutions.

Group Specific Schemes

There are many schemes for promoting access to higher education among weaker sections of society. Some of these are discussed here.

Schemes for Women

The government is striving hard to cater to needs of women regarding higher education. Some women specific schemes are

(I) Promotion of Women in Science & Technology

Ministry of Science & Technology has initiated many schemes for welfare of women.

- o There is provision for state wise scholarships for rural girl students to have access to higher studies in: science & technology at college and university level.
- o For better representation of girl students in higher education, number of scholarships has been increased, because the present number is insufficient.
- o There is provision for awareness program, regarding Science & Technology for women through training, counseling program for teachers and trainers to ensure wider dissemination of information.

(2) Postgraduate Indira Gandhi Scholarship Scheme for Single Girl Child

University Grants Commission has introduced this scheme with an aim to compensate direct cost of girl education to all levels especially for such girls who happen to be the only girl child in their families. This scheme can support post graduate education of single girl child in non professional courses and recognize the value of observance of small family norm as well.

(3) UGC's Post -Doctoral Fellowship to Women Candidates

University Grants Commission has initiated an ambitious scheme of post doctoral fellowship to women candidates for promoting post doctoral studies and tries to make their better representation in the field of higher education.

(4) Quota for Women in Scholarships

Thirty percent seats are reserved in favour of women in Post-matric Scholarship for Minorities, Maulana Azad National Fellowship for Minority Students, Free Coaching for Minority Community, Merit-cum-Means Scheme of Scholarship for Minorities, Scheme of Coaching for Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes etc. 500At seats are reserved in favour of girls in Central Sector Scheme of Scholarship for College and University Students.

Schemes for Minorities

The Ministry of Minority Affairs Was created on 29th January, 2006 to ensure a focussed approach to the issues relating to the minorities and to play a pivotal role in the. overall policy, planning, coordination, evaluation and review of regulatory and development programmes for the benefit of minority communities. Minority specific schemes are as follows-

(1) The National Commission for Minority Educational Institutions

The National Commission for Minority Educational Institutions (NCMEI) was established on 11th November 2004 with mandate to look into specific complaints regarding deprivation or violation of minorities to establish and administer educational institutions of their choice. This Commission is a quasi-judicial body endowed with the powers of a Civil Court. The Commission can make recommendations to the Central Government and the State Governments regarding any matter which directly or indirectly deprives the minority community of their educational rights enshrined in Article 30 of the Constitution.

(2) Scheme of Post-Matric Scholarship for Students Belonging to the Minority Communities

The Prime Minister's New 15 Point Programme for the Welfare of Minorities provides for a post-matric scholarship scheme for meritorious students from minority communities. The scheme came into existence on 29th November, 2007.

This scholarship is awarded to students belonging to the minority communities studying in class XI upto Ph.D. level. The objective of the scheme

is to award scholarships to meritorious students belonging to economically weaker sections of minority community so as to provide them better opportunities for higher education increase their rate of attainment in higher education and enhance their employability. The scholarship is awarded for studies in India in a government or private higher secondary school/college/ university. The annual income of beneficiary's parents/guardian from all sources does not exceed Rs.2 lakh. 30% Slots of scholarship are earmarked for girl students. Four lakh scholarships have been announced for the academic session 2010-2011. The share of Muslims, Christians, Sikhs, Buddhists and Parsis is 291700, 50800, 40560, 16800 and 140 respectively.

(3) Merit-cum-Means Scholarship Scheme for Minority Communities Students

This centrally financed scheme aimed at providing financial assistance to the poor and meritorious students belonging to minority communities to enable them to pursue professional and technical courses at undergraduate and post-graduate levels in recognised courses. These scholarships are available for studies in India only. Every year twenty thousand scholarships are available for distribution among the students of minority communities throughout the country.

Table 2: The Community wise distribution of Merit-cum-Means Scholarship

S.N.	Name of Minority Community	No of Scholarships
1	Muslim	14585
2	Christian	2540
3	Sikh	202S
4	Buddhist	840
5	Parsi	7
Total		20,000

The annual income of the beneficiary/parent or guardian of beneficiary should not exceed Rs. 2.50 lakh from all sources. The scheme is gender sensitive for it reserves 30% scholarship for girls. of each minority community in a state.

(4) Maulana Azad National Fellowship for Minority Students

This scheme is in operation from academic session 2009-2010. The objective of this scheme is to provide integrated five year fellowships in the form of financial assistance to students from minority communities to pursue higher studies such as M. Phil and Ph.D. and it is implemented by the Ministry of

Minority Affairs through UGC. The fellowship under this scheme for minority students is on the pattern of UGC Fellowships awarded to research students pursuing regular and full time M. Phil and Ph. D courses. The number fellowships to be awarded each year is 756. The thirty percent of the fellowship are earmarked for women students. These are integrated five year fellowships for M. Phil & Ph.D course. The income ceiling of the parents/guardian of the candidate for Maulana Azad National Fellowship for minority students is Rs. 2.5 Lakh per annum. The community wise distribution is - 544 for Muslims, 100 for Christian, 74 for Sikhs, 36 for Buddhists and 2 for Parsis. An outlay of Rs.1400 crores has been provided for the 11 th Five- Year Plan to award 25 lakhs scholarships during the plan period (2007-2012).

(5) Free Coaching and Allied Assistance Scheme for the Candidates Belonging to Minority Communities

The scheme aims to empower the minority communities by assisting them as well as those institutions working for them, towards enhancing their skills and capabilities to make them employable. in industries, services and business sectors in addition to the government sector. 30% of the numbers sanctioned for coaching/training are earmarked for girl students/candidates Hundred percent financial assistance is available to the selected coaching/training institutes and the institutes imparting remedial tuition. Stipend is also given for maintenance of the students.

Scheme for Scheduled Tribes

The Ministry of Tribal Affairs was constituted in October 1999 with the objective of providing more focused attention on the integrated socio-economic development of the most under-privileged sections of the Indian society namely, the Scheduled Tribes (STs), in a coordinated and planned manner.

(1) Scheme of Coaching for Scheduled Tribes

The Scheme was started during 4th Plan period. The scheduled tribes coming from deprived families and disadvantaged environment find it difficult to compete with those coming from a socially and economically advantageous background. To promote a more level playing field, and give ST candidates a better chance to succeed in competitive examinations, the Ministry of Tribal Affairs supports a scheme for coaching for disadvantaged ST candidates in quality coaching institutions to enable them to appear in competitive examinations and succeed in obtaining an appropriate job in the public/private sector. Pre-Examination Coaching

Centres run by State Governments/Universities/ Registered Private Institutions. The courses for which the coaching is available includes Civil Services Examination/State Civil Services examination, Entrance Exams for Medical, Engineering, MBA and other professional courses, other exams conducted by U.P.S.C. like CDS, NDA, etc./Staff Selection Commission Exams/Subordinated/Lower Subordinate Services Exam, Central Excise, BSRBs/RRBs, General Insurance Corporation, etc. The total number of ST students admitted shall preferably contain 300% women ST candidates and 5% disabled ST candidates. The income ceiling of candidate is Rs. 2.50 lakh per annum. Union Territories, Universities and private institutions will be given 100% grant.

(2) Central Sector Scholarship Scheme of Top Class Education for ST Students

This Central Sector Scholarship Scheme was introduced from the academic year 2007-08. There are 127 institutes identified under the scheme in both the Government and private sectors covering the field of management, medicine, engineering, law and commercial courses. Each institute has been allocated five awards, with a ceiling of total 635 scholarships per year. The family income of the ST students from all the sources shall not exceed Rs. 2.00 lakh per annum. The ST students will be awarded scholarship covering full tuition fee and, other non-refundable dues in respect of Government/Government-funded institutions. However, there will be a ceiling of Rs. 2.00 lakh per annum per student for private sector institutions and Rs.72 lakh per annum per student for the private sector flying clubs for Commercial Pilot Training In addition to the above, the scholarship also provides for (i) living expenses @ Rs. 2200/- per month per student subject to actuals, (ii) books and stationery @ Rs. 3000/- per annum per student and (iii) cost of a latest computer system along with its accessories limited to Rs. 45000/- as one time assistance during the course. The institute will select the eligible ST students on the basis of merit.

(3) The Scheme of National Overseas Scholarships for Schedule Tribes

The scheme provides financial assistance to students selected for pursuing higher studies abroad in certain subjects at the Masters level, and for Ph. D and Post-Doctoral research programmes. 15 awards per year are sanctioned to ST students. Total income from all sources of the employed candidate or his/her parents/guardians should not exceed Rs. 25,000/- per month. All candidates after having availed of the award under the scheme have to return to India. The awardee is obliged by legal bond to remain in India for 5 years after his return and shall also serve the Government, if he/she continues to be in Government service after return to India, as he/she was before going abroad with award under the scheme.

(4) Post-Matric Scholarship for Scheduled Tribes Students

The objective of the scheme is to provide financial assistance to students belonging to Scheduled Tribes pursuing Post-Matriculation recognized courses in recognized institutions. The scheme covers professional, technical as well as non-

professional and non-technical courses at various levels and the scheme also includes correspondence courses including distance and continuing education. The value of the existing scholarship . includes maintenance allowance, reader charges of blind students, study tour charges, thesis typing/printing charges, book allowance to students pursuing correspondence course and compulsory non-refundable fees charges by the educational institutions. The maintenance allowance for hostlers is between Rs. 2351- p.m, to 7401- and for day scholars from Rs. 140/- p.m. to Rs. 330/- p.m., depending upon the level of courses, The prescribed annual income ceiling of both the parents/guardians, under the scheme is up to Rs. 1,45,000/-, as applicable w.e.f. 1-4-2010.

(5) Rajiv Gandhi National Fellowship for ST Students

The objective of the scheme is to provide fellowships in the form of financial assistance to students belonging to Scheduled Tribes to pursue higher studies such as M. Phil and Ph.D. The scheme is in operation since 2005-06. UGC is the nodal agency for implementing the RGNF scheme for ST students. The total number of fresh fellowships each year is 667.

Scheme for Scheduled Castes

The share of Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes as a percent to total enrolment in higher education has been steadily increasing over the years. However, their enrolment share in higher education is still lower in relation to their total population. The enrolment of SC and ST students as a percentage of total enrolment in higher is 12% and 5% respectively. At the doctoral level the enrolment share of SC and ST is 11% and 4% respectively, The Ministry of Social Justice & Empowerment is the nodal Ministry to oversee the interests of the Scheduled Castes. Though the primary responsibility for promotion of interests of the Scheduled Castes rests with all the Central Ministries in the area of their operations and the State Governments, the Ministry complements their efforts by way of interventions in critical sectors through specifically tailored schemes. These SCs are getting benefits of Rajiv Gandhi National Fellowship Scheme, Free Coaching Scheme, Post-matric Scholarship Scheme and other schemes, more or less on the paten of Scheduled Tribes.

The Poor

The government is taking many steps for education of economically disadvantaged section of society.

(1) Central Sector Scheme of Scholarship for College and University Students

The Department of Higher Education has introduced this scheme for meritorious students from low income families going to colleges/universities for implementation during the XI Five Year Plan period with an. approved outlay of Rs. 1000 crore. The objective of the scheme is to provide financial assistance to meritorious students from low income families to meet a part of their day-to-day

for graduate/postgraduate studies in Colleges and universities and for professional courses, such as Medical, Engineering etc. This is applicable to all categories of students both 'general' and 'reserved'. The scholarship is available @ Rs. 1000/- pin. at Graduation level and Rs. 2000/- per month at Post- Graduation level The scholarship is available to only those students whose parent's income is less than 4.5 lakhs per annum. The scholarship under the scheme is renewable from year to year upto Post-Graduate level in the same stream.

(2)Interest Subsidy on Educational loans

One of the major concerns of the Government is to ensure that nobody is denied Professional education because he or she is poor. A new Scheme has been launched in the year 2009-10 to provide full interest subsidy during the period of moratorium on educational loans for students belonging to economically weaker sections, whose parental income is less than Rs. 4..5 lakh per annum. Loans availed from Scheduled Banks the Educational Loan Scheme of the Indian Banks' Association to pursue technical and professional courses of study are covered under the Scheme of Interest Subsidy.

Scheme for Other Backward Classes

The policy of reservation is recognized as an important instrument of affirmative action in India. The Ministry of Human Resource. Development initiated the Central Educational Institutions (Reservation Admission) Act, 2006 to make special provisions for reservation of seats for the Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, and the Other Backward Classes (OBCs) in admissions to central education institutions. Reservation of 27% seats for the OBCs is implemented in all central educational institutions covered by the Central Educational Institutions (Reservation Admission) Act, 2006. The implementation of the Act was started in a phased manner from the academic session 2008-09. A sum of Rs. 2522 crores was released in 2008-09 for Upgradation of infrastructure and implementation of OBC reservation policy which requires 54% increase in intake capacity within three years. Further, an amount of Rs. 1033 crores was earmarked in 2009-10 for the purpose. The OBCs are also getting benefits of Post-matric scholarships for higher education.

Equal Opportunity Offices

University Grants Commission (UGC) has initiated measures to create Equal Opportunity Offices (EOCs) in all universities. An amount of Rs. 3 lakh per university has been sanctioned to each of the 167 eligible universities. EOCs will help to achieve effective implementation of schemes for all disadvantaged sections of society.

Suggestions

Despite of concerted and enthusiastic efforts of government, constitutional provisions and different acts made for making educational system egalitarian, the

educational system is still monopolized by some sections of society at the cost of others. The different schemes and programs being nm for equity, access and inclusion for disadvantaged sections of society suffers from one or other flaws. Some concrete suggestions in this regard are -

(I) Equity in Admission

Most of the institutions in India adopt either entrance test method of admission or admission based on merit of qualifying examination. However, there may be some institutions offering admission even in field of higher education on the basis of first come first serve method. Both in case of entrance test method and merit based method, the candidates from weaker and disadvantaged sections are the sufferers. Often entrance test are designed in favour of those having access to convent education and a lot of information owing to Information and Communication Technology (ICT). The candidates, who belong to rural background, the poor, women and those from disadvantaged sections of the society; have no or little access to the modem gadgets of ICT, so they are often not well informed of the happenings of all around the world.

The admission tests are seldom attitude based, so this entrance test method also adds to woes of already educationally marginalized persons. In case of merit based admission, the foremost problem is multiplicity of examining bodies. There is no common standard and procedure followed by these boards or universities, and they even do not agree to the limit of passing marks in the classification of students into various divisions. Some boards and universities are liberal in awarding marks and it is not uncommon to see 100 out of 100 in examinations whereas there are some 'primitive' boards of examination conservative in awarding marks that sometimes number of failed students outnumber the passed ones. Different examiners follow their self-styled methods of evaluation and observed self-professed standards of awarding marks. This is perhaps the biggest problem in education system at all levels of education. Needless to say that until the parity in evaluation standards of different examining bodies, is established, the merit based admission system is of little use as far as quality based admission is proclaimed.

There is a difference between merit and intellectual capabilities of a student. A lot of factors intervene in making the potential of student in merit; These factors inter-alia intelligence of the student, their socioeconomic status, parental education, nutritional support, quality of teachers in-the schools and of course the examining bodies. So at the time of admission, based on merit or admission test score, the damage caused by these adverse factors should and must be compensated. This justifies the lowering of standards in admission in favour of those from disadvantaged and weaker sections of the society. But at the same time the academic excellence cannot be sacrificed for the sake of equality and justice. A middle path can show us light.

The admission criteria may be reasonably relaxed in favour of disadvantaged

ones. For example a relaxation of 5% marks may be given to SCs or STs in admission vis-a-vis the marks of last candidate admitted in general category. The very poor quality students admitted often failed to complete their degree or get passed with very poor marks having no use for their further employment. This not only leads to wastage of scarce resources of a developing country like India, but also wastage of time and labour of these students.

(2) Institutional support

Once the students get admitted, institution should offer special support to the needy and poor. These may include-

a) Book Bank-There should be a collection of reasonable number of text books and reference books meant for the particular course. These should be lending to the needful students, so that these students can get rid off economic burden of purchasing books.

b) Tutorial classes-Individual differences do exist among students in a class. The tutorial classes should be opened to all and particularly structured in favor of academically weaker students. These tutorial classes will compensate for private tuitions engaged by students coming from affluent sections.

c) Hostels-Hostel accommodation can compensate for poor atmosphere available for study at home and also for traveling expanses for those coming from remote areas. The hostel accommodation may be given free of charge to the poor ones. It is more crucial for girls, particularly in orthodox societies like ours.

d) Free transport-The institutions may provide free transport facilities to the poor, women and disadvantaged ones. The government may also provide concessional monthly season tickets (MSTs) to students in public transport.

(3) Free-ships and Scholarships

The poor students should be given free admissions. Besides, they may be granted liberal scholarships, but a caution is needed at the time of offering scholarship to the students. The money should go, only in the bands of needful students and that too academic purpose, As scholarships and free ships are compensation for poverty so, it is a thing of caution that only poor students get these. A means test must be applied for identifying the right beneficiaries. Most often, by default scholarships go into hands of rich ones, as many of the institutions offer scholarships based solely on academic performance, for example it has been observed in the case of Rajiv Gandhi National Fellowship. Many rich students are getting fellowships and the poor are left behind. In some cases even the wards and spouses of gazetted officers are getting fellowships. These scholarships should be timely distributed to make them meaningful.

(4) Pre -Examination Coaching

‘To provide level playing field to all competing candidates, pre examination

coaching for admissions in various courses of higher education as well as for various competitive examinations meant for employment in public as well as private sector. Though some coaching schemes are being run by the government but they are not sufficient. These coaching centers are only in the state capitals and in big cities. These must be present at least up to the district level, The coaching schemes must orient and adapt themselves to changing needs of the market Apprenticeship and training program meant for recruiting different technical cadres should also be imparted by these pre examination coaching centers.

Conclusion

The egalitarian society can be built by equal access to education. Not only equal access is necessary, equal exit is also needed. The on-governing schemes and programmes are bound to yield fruitful results.

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